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Conference Abstract

RATIONAL EVIDENCE FOR TAWHEED, RISALAH, AND LIFE AFTER DEATH IN THE VIEW OF SYED ABUL A'LA MAUDUDI

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ABSTRACT

In this chapter of *Islamic Way of Life and Its Fundamental Concepts*, Syed Abul A'la Maududi presents a rational argument for Tawheed (monotheism), Risalah (prophethood), and Akhirah (life after death) as the foundations of Islamic belief. He argues that the order, harmony, and precision of the universe indicate the existence of a single, all-powerful Creator, rejecting atheistic and polytheistic ideologies. The intricate design of nature—from celestial bodies to biological systems—demonstrates the necessity of one supreme authority governing all existence. Maududi also emphasizes the necessity of divine guidance (Risalah). He explains that while human intellect is capable of great discoveries, it is insufficient in establishing absolute moral and ethical standards. Prophethood is essential to provide a comprehensive code of life, ensuring justice, morality, and social harmony. The teachings and character of Prophet Muhammad (PBUH) exemplify divine wisdom and guidance in human affairs. The concept of Akhirah (life after death) is presented as a rational necessity for ultimate justice. Many wrongdoers escape punishment in this world, while the righteous often suffer without reward. Without an afterlife, the concept of justice remains incomplete. Akhirah guarantees moral accountability and ensures that every individual is judged fairly. Maududi systematically refutes materialistic and secular worldviews, presenting Islam as a holistic, rational system that aligns with human nature and intellect. He asserts that

Islamic beliefs are not based on blind faith but on reason, logic, and human experience.

Keywords: Tawheed (Monotheism), Risalah (Prophethood), Akhirah (Life After Death), Islamic Beliefs, Rational Evidence, Divine Guidance, Moral Accountability, Ultimate Justice, Human Intellect and Limitations.

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